

**Salmonella control programme in accordance with Regulation (EC) No.
2160/2003
2012 results**

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Since 2008, the Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR) has assessed data on the prevalence of salmonella in flocks of breeding poultry, laying hens, broilers and turkeys. Published each year, the reports are part of an EU-wide programme to control salmonella. They are based on results from official surveillance by the federal states as well as own checks conducted by the food business operators themselves.

Compared to the previous year, data for 2012 showed a similar or slightly decreased *Salmonella* prevalence for laying hens, broilers and breeding turkeys but an increase in the detected rates for breeding hens and fattening turkeys. In terms of the control-relevant serovars, the agreed target value was reached for all types of poultry covered by the control programmes.

The full version of this BfR Information is available in German on <http://www.bfr.bund.de/cm/343/salmonella-bekaempfungsprogramm-gemaess-verordnung-eg-nr-2160-2003-ergebnisse-fuer-2012.pdf>